

Indications and Outcomes of Tracheostomy Among Patients attending Muhimbili National Hospital 2023-2025

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Introduction

Tracheostomy is a lifesaving procedure widely used for securing the airway in patients with upper airway obstruction, trauma, or prolonged ventilation needs. However, its indications and outcomes in resource-limited settings like Tanzania remain poorly documented. This study aimed to characterize tracheostomy practice at Muhimbili National Hospital, focusing on indications, outcomes, and predictors of adverse outcomes.

Materials and Methods

We conducted a retrospective cross-sectional study of patients who underwent tracheostomy at MNH over 33 months, between January 2023 and October 2025. Data on demographics, indications, procedural urgency, and outcomes were abstracted from theatre registers and patient files. Categorical data were analyzed using the chi-square test of independence, with Fisher's exact test applied when expected cell counts were less than 5. Statistical significance at $p < 0.05$. All analyses were conducted using R (version 4.5.1). Ethical approval was obtained from relevant institutional review boards.

Results

A total of 89 patients underwent tracheostomy during the study period. The cohort was predominantly male (57.3%) with a median age of 56 years (range 1–79). Upper airway obstruction (UAO) was the leading indication (65.2%), driven primarily by laryngeal (28.1%) and hypopharyngeal tumors (12.4%). The overall complication rate was 44.9%. Emergency procedures comprised 38.2% of cases and were the strongest predictor of adverse outcomes—nearly doubling the complication rate (58.8% vs 32.7%, $p = 0.017$) and increasing mortality more than six-fold (26.5% vs 4.1%, $p = 0.004$). Overall in-hospital mortality was 13.5%. Decannulation was achieved in only 12.4%, with 73.0% discharged with a tracheostomy tube in situ, significantly associated with UAO indication ($p = 0.014$).

Conclusion

Tracheostomy at MNH is predominantly performed for UAO secondary to head and neck malignancies. Emergency procedures carry substantially higher morbidity and mortality, underscoring the need for early identification and referral to enable elective intervention.

Keywords

Airway management, Complications, Indications, Outcomes, Post operative care, Post operative complications, Resource-limited settings, Tracheostomy